

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY****DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF ALUMINUM ALLOY PISTON USING CAE TOOLS****Mr. Jadhav Vishal, Dr. R.K. Jain, Mr. Yogendra S.Chauhan**

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ABSTRACT

Recent advancement of technology leads to complex decision in the Engineering field. Thus this paper entails the design and analysis of an IC engine piston using two different aluminum materials that are competitive in market. Piston plays a main role in energy conversation. Failure of piston due to various thermal and mechanical stresses is common and so expensive to replace. The specifications used for this work is related to four stroke single cylinder engine of Hero Karizma ZMR motorcycle. Design of the piston is carried out using SOLIDWORKS software, thermal and stress analysis is performed using Finite Element Analysis (FEA).The best aluminum alloy material is selected based on thermal and stress analysis results. The analysis results are used to optimize piston geometry of best aluminum alloy.

KEYWORDS: Piston, Solid works, thermal, stress analysis.

INTRODUCTION

A piston is a component of reciprocating IC engines. It is the moving component with in a cylinder and is made of gas-tight by piston rings. In an engine, piston is used to transfer force from expanding gas in the cylinder to the crankshaft via a piston rod. Piston endures the cyclic gas pressure and the inertial forces at work, and this working condition may cause the fatigue damage of the piston, such as piston side wear, piston head cracks and so on. So there is a need to optimize the design of piston by considering various parameters in this project the parameters selected are analysis of piston by applying pressure force acting at the top of the piston and thermal analysis of piston at various temperatures at the top of the piston in various strokes. This analysis could be useful for design engineers for modification of piston at the time of design.

PISTON DESIGN FEATURES

1. Have sufficient mechanical strength and stiffness.
2. Can effectively block the heat reached the piston head.
3. High temperature corrosion resistance.
4. Dimensions as compact as possible, in order to reduce the weight of the piston

OBJECTIVES

1. Analytical design of piston using Hero Karizma ZMR specifications.
2. Obtaining design of piston using Solid works 2013 and then imported in ansys 15.0
3. Meshing of design model using ANSYS 15.
4. Analysis of piston by stress analysis and thermal analysis method.
5. Comparing the performance of two aluminum alloy piston under structural and thermal analysis process.
6. Identification of the suitable aluminum alloy material for manufacturing of the piston under specified conditions.

The engine specifications used for this work is a four stroke single cylinder type Hero Karizma ZMR petrol engine.

Table 1: engine specification

PARAMETERS	VALUES
Engine type	Four stroke, petrol engine
Number of cylinders	Single cylinder
Bore	65.5 mm
Stroke	66.2 mm
Maximum power	14.9 KW @ 8000 rpm
Maximum torque	19.7 Nm @ 6500 rpm
Maximum speed	129 Kmph
Compression ratio	9.6:1

PROPERTIES OF MATERIALS

The materials considered for this work are A4032 and A2618 for an IC engine piston. The mechanical and physical properties of aluminum alloys are listed in the table

Table 2: material properties

s. no	PARAMETERS	A4032	A2618
1	Density (kg/m ³)	2684.95	2767.99
2	Poisson's ratio	0.33	0.33
3	Coefficient of thermal expansion (1/K)	79.2×10^{-6}	25.9×10^{-6}
4	Elastic modulus (Gpa)	79	73.7
5	Yield strength (Mpa)	315	420
6	Ultimate tensile strength (Mpa)	380	480
7	Thermal conductivity (W/m ⁰ C)	154	147

METHODOLOGY

Let,

IP = indicated power produced inside the cylinder (W)

N = engine speed (rpm)

L = length of stroke (mm)

A = cross-section area of cylinder (mm²)

m_p = mass of the piston (Kg)

V = volume of the piston (mm³)

t_H = thickness of piston head (mm)

D = cylinder bore (mm)

P_{max} = maximum gas pressure or explosion pressure (Mpa)

σ_i = allowable tensile strength (Mpa)

σ_{ut} = ultimate tensile strength (Mpa)

K = thermal conductivity (W/m K)

T_c = temperature at the centre of the piston head (K)

T_e = temperature at the edge of the piston head (K)

HCV = Higher Calorific Value of fuel (KJ/Kg) = 48000 KJ/Kg

BP = brake power of the engine per cylinder (KW)

C = ratio of heat absorbed by the piston to the total heat developed in the cylinder = 5% or 0.05

t_1 = radial thickness of ring (mm)

P_w = allowable radial pressure on cylinder wall (N/mm²) = 0.025 Mpa

σ_p = permissible tensile strength for ring material (N/mm²) = 110 N/mm²

t_2 = axial thickness of piston ring (mm)

b_1 = width of top lands (mm)

b_2 = width of ring lands (mm)

t_3 = thickness of piston barrel at the open end (mm)

l_s = length of skirt (mm)

d_o = outer diameter of piston pin (mm)

Mechanical efficiency of the engine (η) = 70 %.

H = Brake power (B.P)/ Indicating power (I.P)

Therefore, I.P = B.P / η = 14.9/0.9 = 16.55 KW

Also, I.P = $P \times A \times L \times N / 2$

I.P = $P \times \pi D^2 / 4 \times L \times N / 2$

Substituting the values we have

$$16.55 \times 1000 = \frac{P \times \pi (0.0655)^2}{4} \times (0.0662) \times \frac{6500}{2 \times 60}$$

$P = 1.3566$ Mpa

Maximum Pressure = $P_{max} = 10 \times P$

= $10 \times 1.356 = 13.56$ Mpa

PROCEDURE FOR DESIGN OF PISTON

$$t_H = \sqrt{\frac{3pD^2}{16\sigma_t}}$$

Where: p is the maximum gas pressure (Mpa)

D is the bore diameter (mm)

σ_t is the permissible stress (Mpa)

$$t_1 = D \times \sqrt{\frac{3P_w}{\sigma_p}}$$

Where P_w is the Pressure of fuel on cylinder wall (0.025N/mm²-0.042N/mm²)

$t_2 = 0.7t_1$ to t_1

or

$$t_2 = \frac{D}{10 \times n_r}$$

Where: n_r is the number of rings

$b_1 = t_H$ to $1.2 t_H$

$b_2 = 0.7t_2$ to t_2

$t_3 = 0.03 \times D + t_1 + 4.9$

$l_s = (0.6D$ to $0.8D)$

$d_0 = (0.28D$ to $0.38D)$

The geometric values considered for design of piston in Solidworks 2013.

Table 3: geometric values

s.no	DIMENSIONS	SIZE (mm)
1	Cylinder bore (D)	65.5
2	Thickness of the piston head (t_H)	8.03
3	Radial thickness of ring (t_1)	1.710
4	Axial thickness of ring (t_2)	2.183
5	Width of top land (b_1)	8.03
6	Width of other land (b_2)	2.183
7	Maximum thickness of barrel (t_3)	8.575
8	Length of the skirt (l_s)	39.3
9	Piston pin diameter (d_0)	18.34

BOUNDARY CONDITIONS AND LOADS

Figure 1: Boundary conditions

1. Maximum pressure load at the top surface of the piston crown 13.56 Mpa
2. Temperature at the top surface of the piston crown 1500^0 C
3. Piston pin holes are fixed $D_X = D_Y = D_Z = 0$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The constructed piston in Solid works is analyzed using ANSYS V15.0 and the results are depicted below. Combustion of gases in the combustion chamber exerts pressure on the head of the piston during power stroke. Fixed support has given at surface of pinhole. Because the piston will move from top dead center to bottom dead center with the help of fixed support at pinhole.

A. A4032 aluminum alloy piston

Figure 2: Total deformation

Figure 3: von mises stress

Figure 4: Total heat flux

B. A2618 ALUMINUM ALLOY PISTON

Figure5: Total deformation

Figure 6: von-misses stress

Figure 7: Total heat flux

Table 4: Results of aluminum alloy material

s. no	PARAMETERS	A4032	A2618
1	Total deformation (mm)	0.051334	0.055088
2	Von-misses stress (Mpa)	304.83	305.18
3	Total heat flux (W/mm ²)	1.0787	1.1146
4	Mass (kg)	0.2209	0.2277

CONCLUSION

The piston plays a major role in the performance of the engine performance, materials of the piston is made up of impacts the strength of the piston. The maximum stress intensity is on the bottom surface of the piston crown in both the materials, as it is expected. The maximum displacement is absorbed at the top of the piston of 4032 and A2618. The highest value of maximum temperature found in piston is due to thermal conductivity of the materials and the total maximum heat flux is absorbed in both the piston materials. Results comparison between two alloys is found approximately same. Thus further research can be carried with the advance materials and different designing, analysis tools.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support of school of Mechanical Engineering, ITM University, Gwalior, India.

REFERENCES

1. "Thermal analysis of aluminum alloy piston" by B.A.Devan¹, G. Ravinder Reddy² International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering Research (IJETER), vol. 3 no6, ISSN 2347-3983. Pages: 511 -515 (2015)
2. Ajay Raj Singh, Dr. Pushpendra Kumar Sharma, "Design, Analysis and Optimization of Three Aluminum Piston Alloys Using FEA" Int. Journal of Engineering Research and Applications, ISSN : 2248-9622, Vol. 4, Issue 1 Version 3, January 2014, pp.94-102
3. "Thermal Stress Analysis of a Speculative IC Engine piston using CAE Tools" by Hitesh pandey¹, Avin chandrakar², PM Bhagwat³, int. journal of Engineering Research and Applications (ijera), ISSN :2248-9622, vol.4, issue 11(version-5),November 2014,pp.60-64
4. "Design Analysis and Optimization of Piston Using CAE Tools" by Vaibhav v. mukkawar¹, Nitin d.bhusale². babasahebnaik college of engg, pusad-445204
5. *Isam Jasim Jaber and Ajeet Kumar Rai*, Design and Analysis of IC Engine Piston and Piston-Ring Using CATIA and ANSYS Software, IJMET, Vol.5, 2014
6. "Thermal Analysis and Optimization of I.C. Engine Piston Using Finite Element Method"InternationalJournal of Innovative Research in Science Engineeringand Technology. S.SrikanthReddy,Dr.B.SudheerPremKumar,Vol.2, Issue12, December2013.
7. "Thermal Analysis and Optimization of I.C. Engine Piston Using finite Element Method"by A. R.Bhagat¹, Y. M. Jibhakate ². International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER), Vol.2, Issue.4,July-Aug 2012 pp-2919-2921.
8. K Venkateswara rao¹, Baswaraj Hasu², "Modeling, Analysis and Optimizatoin of Diesel Engine Piston", IJREAT , volume 2, Issue 1, 2014, ISSN: 2320-8791
9. Aditya Kumar Gupta¹, Vinay Kumar Tripathi², "Design Analysis and Optimization of Internal Combustion Engine Piston Using CAE tools ANSYS" ijera.com, ISSN: 2248-9622, vol.4, Issue 11(version -5), November 2014